

DYNAMICS OF ANAEROBIC METABOLISM THRESHOLD (ANMT) AND MAXIMUM HEART RATE (MHR) INDICATORS IN QUALIFIED ROWERS SPECIALIZING IN SPRINTING

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To determine the level of aerobic energy supply mechanism capabilities in rowers, we conducted tests on the anaerobic metabolism threshold (ANMT) and maximum heart rate (MHR). A decrease in blood lactate levels contributes to an increase in the anaerobic metabolism threshold (ANMT), which is an important indicator. This threshold represents the level of load at which the concentration of lactic acid in the blood exceeds 4 mM/l. The Anaerobic Metabolism Threshold (ANMT) is a criterion indicating the body's aerobic abilities and is directly related to results in endurance-based sports. Another important indicator of aerobic capacity is the maximum heart rate. This indicator is considered a factor determining heart performance in qualified athletes. The results of the "Treadmill" test were determined for subjects in the experimental and control groups at the beginning and end of the study. (Table 1)

Table 1

Results of the "Treadmill" test and 200m rowing test obtained at the beginning and end of the pedagogical experiment in the experimental and control groups

No	Indicators	EG		t	p	CG		t	p
		beginning	end			beginning	end		
		$\bar{x} \pm \sigma$	$\bar{x} \pm \sigma$			$\bar{x} \pm \sigma$	$\bar{x} \pm \sigma$		
1	MHR, beats/min	189.7±5.2	197.7±4.3	2.01	<0.05	190.4±5.0	191.7±6.4	1.68	>0.05
	ANACH beats/min	175.7±7.0	184.7±4.6	2.10	<0.05	176.7±7.2	179.1±6.8	1.45	>0.05
2	200 m, s	47.2±2.3	44.2±1.9	2.08	<0.05	46.7±2.5	45.8±1.9	1.77	>0.05

Note: MHR-Maximum heart rate, ANACH-Anaerobic exchange threshold

No statistically significant differences were observed between the results obtained at the beginning of the study in each group [p>0.05]. At the end of the

study, the anaerobic exchange threshold (ANACH) of the subjects in the experimental group was 184.7, and the maximum heart rate (MHR) was 197.7. For the subjects in the control group, these indicators were 179.1 and 191.7, respectively. This demonstrates that there are statistically significant differences between the indicators of the experimental and control groups. The indicators of the subjects in the experimental group show superiority over those of the control group [$p < 0.05$]. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Results of the subjects in the experimental and control groups obtained at the beginning of the study for MHR, ANACH, and 200 m rowing.

Figure 2. Results of the subjects in the experimental and control groups obtained at the beginning of the study for MHR, ANACH, and 200 m rowing.

To determine the state of special and general endurance, as well as special work capacity, we used the 200-meter rowing test. The pre-study results of the subjects in the experimental and control groups were nearly identical, with no statistically significant differences between them [$p>0.05$]. At the end of the study, the average time for the 200-meter rowing test in the experimental group was 44.2 seconds, while in the control group it was 45.8 seconds. We can observe statistically significant differences between the indicators of the experimental and control groups. The subjects in the experimental group achieved higher results compared to those in the control group [$p<0.05$].

Thus, the analysis of the research results demonstrates the high effectiveness of our developed load distribution and applied methods in planning training loads of various directions during the annual training period for qualified sprint kayakers.

Conclusion: Indicators of the anaerobic exchange threshold (ANACH) and maximum heart rate (MHR) of qualified sprint canoeists are important criteria for determining their level of functional preparedness. The results of the study showed that the dynamics of these indicators are directly related to the athletes' adaptation to physical loads and the state of their cardiovascular system. Analysis of ANACH and MHR indicators allows for individualized planning of the training process, scientifically determining the volume of loads, and increasing their effectiveness. This serves as an important factor in achieving high sports results.

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